

THE LAWS OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *In this article, the speech defects that are common among children of preschool age and the development of children's speech by solving them positively and their correctly organized stages are mentioned. It has been described about the defects that will occur later if it is not formed*

Keywords: *pre-school education, development, speech, vocabulary, speech enrichment, speech standards, didactic materials, methods, didactic speech.*

It is known that a child's speech develops as a result of following the rules of the language, perceiving the speech of adults and his own creative activity. Thus, language and speech are the psychological development of an older child before school, as well as early memory, thinking, perception, emotion and passion are two important tools.

The first rule: the ability to perceive speech in the native language depends on the training of the muscles of the child's speech organs (therefore, it is important to pay sufficient attention to the training of the speech organs in order to improve the pronunciation of words, phrases and sentences).

The second rule: Understanding the meaning of speech depends on the acquisition of lexical and grammatical rules of speech by the child.

The third rule: Mastering the expressiveness of speech depends on the child's tendency to understand the expressive means of phonetics, lexicon and grammar (it is necessary to teach older children to understand the expressiveness of speech and achieve the mastery of this feeling by the child).

The fourth rule: Enrichment of speech depends, first of all, on improving speech skills (if the formation of the speech of an older preschool child was successful at the previous age stage, then the process of enriching speech and mastering it will be easier and faster). In addition, according to the researchers, the speed of speech enrichment depends on the development of language perception, cognitive abilities (sensing, memory, perception, thinking), willpower.

The fifth rule: The acquisition of speech norms depends on the development of language perception. In learning children's speech, it is important to form the habit of using punctuation marks and the ability to remember. It has already been proven in the science of native language methodology that the period of a person's life, mainly before school, is effective in the traditional use of elements of the native language in standard speech.

When solving a complex of issues related to the development of speech of older children of preschool age, the following are taken into account:

1. The human instinct of knowledge, innate curiosity is realized through speech.
2. A child learns about the world through speech. According to psychologists, knowledge about the environment is acquired through speech.

From this, it can be concluded that introducing children to the environment creates a wide range of opportunities for the development of speech. Accordingly, educators guide the speech of

older children by introducing them to the environment. In order to achieve the effectiveness of children's speech development, it is important to take into account the characteristics of the child's level of knowledge, interest and personal abilities. It has been found that the role of brain activity in controlling all movements and behavior of children of preschool age increases. That is, children seek to know and evaluate the actions of the management, the events that are happening around them. Accordingly, the types of activities performed by children of preschool age become diverse and meaningful. So, productive types of children's activities play a big role in the development of speech. The system of mutual relations between children is formed at a high level in jointly organized games. Activities such as socially useful work and study are starting to play an increasingly important role. At the same time, the social motives of work, which are manifested in order to help peers with something, to bring some benefit to them, become more significant, that is, they become noticeable. Pre-school age children begin to control their behavior more reasonably. Children clearly understand the meaning of the tasks set before them by the teacher, and they strive to complete the task independently and flawlessly. All of these serve as important conditions for the development of speech. It is known that achieving any success in education depends on upbringing. Therefore, it is necessary to pay a certain amount of attention to the formation of the moral behavior of preschool children. Goodness, modesty, justice, conscientiousness and the correct moral image should be found in them. In order to develop speech more effectively, it is necessary to define and systematically expand children's ideas about surrounding objects (life and work of the person, animals, plants, underwater world). In the plan to increase the effectiveness of speech development, it is important to conduct walks and trips not only for simple observations (observations) on surrounding objects, but also for learning. At this point, we need to determine what can be achieved by studying the surrounding objects. For this, first of all, it is necessary to group the surrounding resources related to speech development. When studying the environment (by educators or parents), children should not just observe, but also see objects, their parts, elements, perceive processes, events, and think about them. In order to achieve this, the educator is tasked with comparing, comparing, separating, summarizing, analyzing and using other similar methods. In addition, during the learning process, it is important to involve older children of preschool age in the types of work that are convenient for them (cleaning ditches, softening the base of trees, taking care of flowers). This approach is related to the fact that when a person does something with his own hands, he remembers it more and more fully. With this method, the deficiencies in the connected speech of my older children before school are filled by memorizing the names of objects and objects verbatim.

The development of speech of older children of preschool age largely depends on the correct solution of the following things:

- didactic materials for the development of speech (speech of the teacher and parents aimed at a certain goal, fairy tales, songs, stories that are read or told to children);
- methods and methods of education used to master didactic materials;
- organization of education (sorting of surrounding objects, planning related speech development).
- Based on the content of the educational material, some methods of learning it, and the principles related to them, the teacher should plan all the work related to the development of speech.

We have come to the conclusion that in the process of conducting research on the same problem, it will be good to work based on the following didactic principles in terms of speech development:

- to understand the speech material for training the organs of speech and the hand;
- understanding the importance of speech and developing lexical and grammatical skills;
- assessment of expressiveness of speech. For this, it is appropriate to choose didactic material that develops certain emotions in older children of preschool age;
- the principle of developing a feeling of love for the mother tongue (this involves the organization of education for children, in particular, on the acquisition of the tradition of using the facts of the mother tongue in speech
- comparing written speech on a specific topic with oral speech;
- gradual enrichment of speech.

A high level of speech development of children of preschool age can be achieved thanks to the following:

- awareness of the literary standards and rules of the language;
- to be able to express one's opinions freely;
- ability to communicate, deal with adults and peers;
- to be able to listen to the interlocutor, to ask (ask a question correctly), to answer, to object, and if necessary to explain and explain. It is necessary to pay special attention to the development of dialogical and monologic speech in the development of the speech of children of preschool age.

On the basis of the above, Preschool children learn dialogic speech relatively easily. This is expressed by the following: children always hear dialogic speech at home and in kindergarten. In addition, children communicate with each other and mainly use dialogic speech.

According to methodical literature, the literary language is based on monologic speech. That is why speech development is important in the educational system. Monological speech shows an organized system of thoughts (sounds) expressed in the form of logical coherent sentences on a specific topic and directed to influence others.

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